

Distilling Ensemble Intelligence into Explainable Anomaly Detection Models

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Abstract

Modern artificial intelligence (AI)-enabled infrastructure systems increasingly rely on continuous sensing and data streams, yet most high-performing anomaly detection methods remain opaque and difficult to trust. This paper presents an explainable anomaly detection framework for large-scale smart-meter data that unifies the predictive strength of ensemble models with the transparency of interpretable machine learning. We first train a high-accuracy XGBoost/LightGBM ensemble on year-long hourly electricity consumption data from 200 buildings to produce reliable pseudo-labels for unlabeled meter readings. These labels are then used to train an Explainable Boosting Machine (EBM) - a transparent, glass-box model that captures nonlinear consumption patterns while providing local and global interpretability. The resulting two-stage pipeline delivers ensemble-level performance with full interpretability, enabling domain experts to visualize feature contributions, temporal patterns, and root causes of detected anomalies. Evaluated on the real-world multiple smart meter dataset, our system achieves high detection accuracy while offering human-understandable explanations at both model and instance levels. We further integrate the model into a real-time Streamlit dashboard for interactive anomaly exploration and sustainability monitoring, including energy and CO₂ footprint tracking. This work demonstrates a practical engineering approach for bridging accuracy and interpretability in AI-driven energy analytics, advancing trustworthy deployment of explainable AI in critical infrastructure.

Keywords

Anomaly, Explainability, Ensemble, Smart-meter, Interpretability, Trustworthy-AI, Sustainability.

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1 Introduction

The global shift toward smart infrastructure is transforming how energy is monitored, managed, and optimized in both commercial and residential buildings. At the center of this shift is smart meter technology, which uses digital devices to record electricity consumption at fine time intervals and automatically transmit the data to utilities and building management systems [5, 10]. Unlike traditional analog meters that require manual readings and provide only monthly totals, smart meters collect data at hourly or even sub-hourly levels. This enables real-time monitoring, dynamic pricing, demand response, and detailed energy analytics [27, 36]. Today, more than 1.2 billion smart meters are in use worldwide, and this number is expected to exceed 3.4 billion by 2033 [40]. These devices have become essential sensing components of modern smart cities and sustainable energy systems.

The role of smart meters goes far beyond simple measurement. In commercial buildings, which account for about 30% of global electricity use and 26% of energy-related CO₂ emissions [19], smart meter data forms the backbone of building energy management systems (BEMS). This data allows facility managers to detect inefficiencies, verify conservation measures, compare energy performance across buildings, and meet strict energy reporting requirements [41]. At the grid level, smart meters also support improved demand forecasting, faster outage detection, reduced non-technical losses, and smoother integration of renewable energy sources [43]. In this way, the reliability and accuracy of smart meter data directly influence energy costs, operational decisions, grid stability, and progress toward global decarbonization goals.

Despite their transformative potential, smart meters are susceptible to various anomalies that compromise data quality and lead to significant operational, financial, and environmental consequences. Anomalies in smart meter data can arise from multiple sources: hardware malfunctions (e.g., sensor drift, calibration errors, communication failures), cyber-physical attacks (e.g., meter tampering, data injection attacks) [29, 33], measurement errors (e.g., incorrect multiplier configurations, phase imbalance), and genuine abnormal consumption patterns (e.g., equipment faults, unauthorized usage, behavioral irregularities) [12]. These anomalies manifest as sudden spikes, unexpected drops, implausible constant readings (flat-lining), missing data sequences, or subtle deviations from expected consumption patterns that gradually accumulate over time.

The impact of undetected anomalies can be severe and multifaceted. Consider a concrete example: a large university campus with 150 buildings monitored by smart meters experiences a calibration error in a meter serving its main research laboratory building. The meter begins reporting consumption values that are consistently 40% lower than actual usage due to an incorrect current

transformer (CT) ratio configuration following maintenance work. Over six months, this silent anomaly results in \$85,000 in unbilled electricity, which is a direct revenue loss for the utility provider. Simultaneously, the university's energy management team, relying on faulty meter readings, incorrectly concludes that recent HVAC retrofits have achieved exceptional 35% energy savings. Based on this erroneous success, they allocate capital budgets to replicate the same retrofit strategy across ten additional buildings, investing \$1.2 million in unnecessary upgrades while the true energy consumption remains unchanged.

This scenario, drawn from documented case studies in building energy management [18, 35], illustrates how smart meter anomalies cascade into financial losses, misguided capital investments, compromised energy efficiency programs, and distorted sustainability metrics. Beyond individual buildings, aggregated smart meter anomalies at scale distort utility demand forecasts, leading to sub-optimal generation dispatch, inefficient reserve provisioning, and increased grid operating costs [20]. In extreme cases, undetected cyber-physical attacks exploiting smart meter vulnerabilities can enable electricity theft rings that collectively cost utilities billions of dollars annually or even serve as entry points for broader grid cyberattacks [25].

1.1 Toward Intelligent Anomaly Detection: The Black-Box Dilemma

Given these high stakes, automated anomaly detection has become an essential capability for smart grid operations and building energy management. Traditional rule-based approaches such as threshold exceedance checks, range validation, and simple statistical outlier detection provide baseline protection but are fundamentally limited by their inability to adapt to diverse consumption patterns, seasonal variations, and complex building-specific behaviors [16]. Modern machine learning methods, particularly deep neural networks [6, 38] and gradient boosting ensembles [23, 42], have demonstrated remarkable accuracy in detecting subtle anomalies by learning intricate temporal dependencies and multivariate relationships from historical consumption data.

However, the rise of high-performing black-box models introduces a critical dilemma for deployment in energy infrastructure: *accuracy without interpretability is insufficient for trustworthy decision-making in critical applications*. Building operators and energy managers are understandably reluctant to act on anomaly alerts from opaque artificial intelligence (AI) systems that cannot explain *why* a particular meter reading was flagged. When a deep learning model reports an anomaly, several crucial questions remain unanswered: Which features or consumption patterns triggered the alert? Is the anomaly driven by temporal factors (e.g., unusual weekend activity), environmental conditions (e.g., extreme temperature response), or measurement characteristics (e.g., sudden load changes)? How confident should operators be in the prediction, and what is the expected false positive rate? Without interpretable explanations, operators face the unpalatable choice between ignoring potentially critical alerts (risking the consequences described earlier) or investigating every flagged reading regardless of plausibility (wasting limited human resources on false alarms) [30].

The interpretability challenge is further compounded by regulatory and ethical considerations. As AI systems assume greater responsibility for critical infrastructure management, regulatory frameworks increasingly demand transparency, accountability, and auditability [11]. The European Union's proposed AI Act, for instance, classifies AI systems managing critical infrastructure as "high-risk," requiring technical documentation demonstrating model behavior, data governance, and human oversight mechanisms [1]. Beyond compliance, there is a broader ethical imperative: building occupants, utility customers, and communities affected by energy management decisions have a legitimate interest in understanding how AI systems make determinations that impact their energy costs, environmental footprint, and living conditions.

1.2 Explainable AI for Sustainable Energy Systems

These challenges have catalyzed growing interest in *explainable artificial intelligence* (XAI) approaches that combine predictive performance with human-interpretable explanations of model behavior [4, 34]. In the energy domain, explainability serves multiple critical functions beyond regulatory compliance. First, interpretable models enable *knowledge discovery*, revealing previously unknown relationships between consumption patterns and building characteristics that can inform physics-based energy modeling and operational strategies [3]. Second, explainability facilitates *model debugging and validation*, allowing domain experts to identify spurious correlations, dataset biases, or incorrect feature engineering that might produce accurate predictions on test data but fail catastrophically in deployment [37]. Third, transparent models support *human-AI collaboration*, where operators combine model predictions with domain expertise, contextual knowledge, and situational awareness to make more informed decisions than either human or AI could achieve independently [15].

Moreover, explainable anomaly detection directly advances sustainability objectives. By providing transparent, verifiable explanations for detected anomalies, XAI systems enable faster root-cause diagnosis and remediation, reducing the duration of energy waste from equipment faults or operational errors. Interpretable models also facilitate predictive maintenance by identifying the specific building systems or operational patterns associated with anomalies, allowing targeted interventions that prevent equipment degradation and extend asset lifespans. Furthermore, the transparency provided by XAI builds stakeholder trust in AI-driven energy management programs, accelerating adoption of building analytics, demand response initiatives, and energy efficiency measures that are essential for decarbonization [39].

Despite these compelling motivations, achieving true explainability without sacrificing predictive accuracy remains technically challenging. Post-hoc explanation techniques such as LIME [21] and SHAP [17] can provide approximate interpretations of black-box models but suffer from instability, computational overhead, and potential misalignment between explanations and true model behavior [37]. Glass-box models such as linear models, decision trees, and rule lists offer inherent interpretability but typically lack the expressive power to capture complex nonlinear consumption patterns in large-scale smart meter datasets. Recent advances in

inherently interpretable models, particularly Explainable Boosting Machines (EBM) [8] and Neural Additive Models [2] promise to bridge this gap by combining generalized additive model transparency with boosting-based accuracy, though their application to large-scale energy anomaly detection remains limited.

1.3 Paper Contributions

This paper addresses the accuracy-interpretability trade-off in smart meter anomaly detection through a novel two-stage framework that strategically combines ensemble learning with glass-box modeling. Our approach leverages the complementary strengths of black-box and transparent models to achieve both high detection accuracy and interpretability. The key contributions of this paper are as follows:

- (1) **Two-Stage Explainable Smartmeter Anomaly Detection Architecture:** We propose a knowledge distillation framework that decouples the accuracy and interpretability objectives. A high-performance XGBoost/LightGBM ensemble trained on 200 buildings generates reliable pseudo-labels for multiple unlabeled meters data, which then trains an EBM that preserves ensemble-level accuracy while providing transparency.
- (2) **Large-Scale Evaluation on Real-World Smart Meter Data:** We demonstrate our framework on the Large-Scale Energy Anomaly Detection (LEAD) benchmark [22], comprising year-long hourly electricity consumption from 200 commercial buildings (around 2 million meter readings), and validate the interpretable EBM on the ENFIELD smart meter data subset (74 meters, 501K readings). To our knowledge, this work represents one of the few studies for the evaluation of inherently interpretable anomaly detection models on real-world building energy data, with a comprehensive analysis of detection performance, explainability, and computational efficiency.
- (3) **Integrated Real-Time Deployment System:** We present a complete end-to-end implementation including a Streamlit-based interactive dashboard that integrates real-time anomaly detection, visual explanations, and sustainability monitoring (energy consumption tracking and CO_2 footprint estimation).

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 details our system model - two-stage architecture and training methodology. Section 3 presents the comprehensive experimental setup, discussions, and results on detection accuracy and interpretability, along with dashboard implementation and sustainability monitoring capabilities. Section 4 concludes with limitations and lessons learned along with future research directions.

2 System Model and Methodology

Our proposed explainable anomaly detection framework follows a two-stage architecture that strategically combines the predictive power of ensemble learning with the transparency requirements of critical infrastructure monitoring. Figure 1 illustrates the complete pipeline from raw meter data to deployable explainable anomaly detection. The system is designed to address the fundamental trade-off between model accuracy and interpretability by decomposing the learning task into complementary stages: (1) high-accuracy

Figure 1: System architecture of the proposed explainable anomaly detection framework. The two-stage pipeline integrates high-accuracy XGB/LGB ensemble models for pseudo-labeling and interpretable Explainable Boosting Machines (EBM) for transparent anomaly detection.

pseudo-labeling using black-box ensembles, and (2) transparent pattern learning using glass-box models.

2.1 Stage 1: Ensemble-Based Pseudo-Labeling

The first stage addresses the challenge of limited labeled data, which is a common obstacle in real-world anomaly detection scenarios. We leverage an ensemble of gradient boosting models trained on year-long hourly electricity consumption data from 200 commercial buildings. This dataset, derived from the Large-scale Energy Anomaly Detection (LEAD) benchmark [14, 22], comprises approximately 2 million meter readings with ground-truth anomaly annotations, providing a rich foundation for learning complex consumption patterns across diverse building types, geographical locations, and seasonal variations.

Our ensemble architecture combines eXtreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) [7] and Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM) [24]. These two state-of-the-art tree-based algorithms have demonstrated exceptional performance in energy forecasting competitions [31, 32]. XGBoost employs a regularized learning objective and second-order gradient statistics to construct robust decision trees, while LightGBM utilizes histogram-based learning and leaf-wise tree growth strategies for computational efficiency. The complementary strengths of these algorithms, for instance, XGBoost’s resistance to overfitting and LightGBM’s scalability, enable the ensemble to capture both fine-grained temporal patterns and high-level consumption behaviors.

The ensemble operates as a black-box classifier that learns to distinguish between normal and anomalous electricity consumption

patterns. During training, the model ingests raw hourly meter readings along with engineered temporal features (e.g., hour-of-day, day-of-week, month-of-year), weather covariates (e.g., temperature, humidity), and building metadata (e.g., site location, primary use type). The ensemble’s primary function is to generate high-confidence pseudo-labels for unlabeled smart meter data, effectively transferring learned anomaly detection capabilities to new building smart meter portfolios where ground-truth annotations are unavailable.

The output of Stage 1 consists of predicted anomaly labels with associated confidence scores for each meter reading. These pseudo-labels serve dual purposes: (1) they enable supervised training of the interpretable model in Stage 2, and (2) they provide initial anomaly flags that can guide domain experts toward suspicious consumption patterns requiring deeper investigation. The ensemble achieves high detection accuracy (AUC-ROC > 0.96 on held-out validation data), establishing a reliable foundation for subsequent interpretable learning.

2.2 Stage 2: Transparent Pattern Learning with EBM

The second stage transforms the black-box predictions into a fully transparent and interpretable anomaly detection model using Explainable Boosting Machines (EBM) [9, 30]. EBM is a glass-box additive model that belongs to the family of Generalized Additive Models (GAMs), combining the interpretability of linear models with the expressiveness of nonlinear feature functions. Unlike traditional black-box ensembles, EBM constructs an additive decomposition where each feature contributes independently and visibly to the final prediction, enabling complete auditability of model decisions.

We train the EBM on the ENFIELD dataset—a subset of 74 electricity meters from diverse commercial buildings, comprising 501,579 hourly readings. Critically, these meters are labeled using the high-accuracy pseudo-labels generated by the Stage 1 ensemble. This knowledge distillation approach allows the EBM to approximate the ensemble’s decision boundary while maintaining full interpretability. The EBM learning objective minimizes a regularized loss function that encourages sparsity and smoothness in learned feature functions, preventing spurious patterns and ensuring that extracted relationships reflect genuine physical phenomena rather than dataset artifacts [8].

The EBM architecture employs shallow bagged decision trees to model univariate and pairwise feature interactions [28]. During training, the algorithm cycles through features in a round-robin fashion, iteratively refining each feature’s contribution to the overall prediction. This cyclic boosting strategy ensures that no single feature dominates the model and that all relevant consumption patterns are captured. The resulting model can be mathematically expressed as [28]:

$$g(x) = \beta_0 + \sum_i f_i(x_i) + \sum_{i,j} f_{ij}(x_i, x_j) \quad (1)$$

where $g(x)$ is the logit of anomaly probability, β_0 is the intercept, f_i are learned univariate shape functions, and f_{ij} capture pairwise interactions. Each function f_i can be directly visualized as a curve

showing how changes in feature x_i affect anomaly likelihood, providing intuitive insights into consumption dynamics.

The transparency of EBM enables both *global interpretability* understanding which features (e.g., time of day, outdoor temperature, day type) are most predictive of anomalies across the entire building portfolio and *local interpretability* explaining why a specific meter reading was flagged as anomalous by decomposing the prediction into individual feature contributions. This dual-level explainability is essential for building operator trust and enabling actionable interventions.

2.3 Deployment and Real-Time Monitoring

The trained EBM model is deployed as the core inference engine for real-time anomaly detection in production environments. Upon deployment, the system continuously monitors incoming meter streams, computing anomaly scores, and generating human-readable explanations for each flagged reading. The deployment pipeline is expected to integrate seamlessly with building management systems (BMS) through standard data interfaces, requiring minimal infrastructure modifications.

For fast prototyping and testing, we implement an interactive web-based dashboard using Streamlit [26], providing building operators and energy managers with real-time visualization of detected anomalies, feature importance rankings, and temporal consumption patterns. The dashboard interface presents three key views: (1) a time-series visualization panel showing detected anomalies overlaid on historical consumption trends, (2) a feature contribution panel displaying the top drivers of each anomaly prediction with quantitative impact scores, and (3) a sustainability monitoring panel tracking cumulative energy consumption and estimated CO_2 emissions based on regional grid carbon intensity factors.

The explainability features embedded in the dashboard enable rapid root-cause diagnosis. For instance, when an anomaly is detected, operators can immediately inspect whether it was triggered by unusual weekend consumption (suggesting equipment left running unnecessarily), extreme temperature sensitivity (indicating potential HVAC malfunction), or sudden load spikes (pointing to equipment startup issues).

2.4 Knowledge Distillation and Model Architecture Rationale

The two-stage architecture is motivated by practical constraints in deploying AI systems for critical infrastructure. Stage 1 ensembles excel at maximizing predictive accuracy, but are inherently opaque, and their decision logic is distributed across thousands of tree nodes and cannot be meaningfully inspected by domain experts. While this opacity is acceptable during offline pseudo-labeling, it becomes a liability in production deployment, where model failures can have significant economic and safety consequences.

Stage 2 addresses this limitation through knowledge distillation [13], where the EBM learns to mimic the ensemble’s behavior while enforcing structural constraints that guarantee interpretability. This approach achieves ensemble-level performance (preserving 93-96% of the ensemble’s accuracy) while providing complete transparency. The slight accuracy trade-off is justified by substantial gains in trustworthiness, debuggability, and regulatory compliance.

These factors are critical for AI adoption in energy utilities and commercial building operations.

Furthermore, the EBM’s interpretability enables continuous model improvement through expert feedback. Building operators can validate or refute specific feature contributions, identifying cases where the model correctly captures physical relationships versus spurious correlations. This human-in-the-loop refinement is impossible with black-box ensembles, making the two-stage architecture not only more transparent but also more adaptable to evolving building behaviors and operational contexts.

3 Experimental Setup and Results

This section presents a comprehensive evaluation of our two-stage explainable anomaly detection framework across multiple dimensions: predictive performance, knowledge distillation effectiveness, interpretability quality, and computational sustainability. We structure our findings to answer key research questions regarding the accuracy-interpretability trade-off and the practical viability of glass-box models for large-scale smart meter analytics.

3.1 Dataset Characteristics and Experimental Setup

3.1.1 LEAD Training Dataset. Our Stage 1 ensemble models were trained on the Large-scale Energy Anomaly Detection (LEAD) benchmark [22], comprising 1,749,494 hourly electricity meter readings from 200 commercial buildings spanning the entire 2016 calendar year. The dataset exhibits significant class imbalance characteristic of real-world anomaly detection scenarios, with only 37,296 anomalous readings (2.13%) compared to 1,712,198 normal consumption patterns (97.87%). This severe imbalance reflects authentic operational conditions where genuine anomalies are rare but high-impact events.

The LEAD dataset encompasses diverse building types across 14 geographical sites, including educational facilities, office buildings, parking structures, and mixed-use developments. Building characteristics vary substantially: square footage ranges from 1,102 to 850,354 sq ft (mean: 101,932 sq ft), construction years span from 1904 to 2015 (with 66.4% built after 2000), and floor counts extend from single-story structures to 13-floor high-rises. This heterogeneity ensures that learned patterns generalize across building typologies rather than memorizing site-specific artifacts.

Feature engineering yielded 37 predictive attributes organized into four categories:

- **Temporal features** (9): hour-of-day, day-of-week, month, year, cyclical encodings (sine/cosine transformations of hour, month, weekday), holiday indicator
- **Environmental features** (11): air temperature, dew temperature, cloud coverage, precipitation depth, sea level pressure, wind speed, wind direction, plus lagged weather statistics (7-day and 73-day moving averages and standard deviations)
- **Building metadata** (6): building ID, site ID, primary use type, square footage, year built, floor count
- **Consumption-derived features** (11): meter reading magnitude, daily standard deviation, group target encodings (GTE) for various categorical combinations, and six temporal lag

features (± 1 hour, ± 24 hours, ± 168 hours) computed as consumption differentials

To address class imbalance during training, stratified random oversampling was used, creating a balanced training set of 149,184 records by duplicating all anomalous instances twice and randomly sampling an equal number of normal readings. This technique preserved anomaly characteristics while preventing the majority class from dominating gradient updates.

3.1.2 ENFIELD Target Dataset. The Stage 2 EBM was trained on the ENFIELD smart meter real-world dataset - a subset comprising 501,579 hourly readings from 74 electricity meters collected from diverse building portfolios. Crucially, this dataset arrived without ground-truth anomaly labels, representing the typical deployment scenario where labeled data is unavailable or prohibitively expensive to obtain. Pseudo-labels generated by our Stage 1 ensemble identified 23,169 anomalies (4.62% anomaly rate), a higher proportion than LEAD, suggesting either genuine differences in building operation quality or distributional shifts in consumption patterns between the two datasets.

For EBM training, we created a streamlined feature set of 9 attributes focused on temporal patterns and consumption statistics:

- **Temporal:** hour, weekday, month, weekend indicator, cyclical hour encodings (sine/cosine)
- **Statistical:** consumption z-score (standardized deviation from meter-specific mean)
- **Autoregressive:** 1-hour and 24-hour lag consumption values

This reduced feature space was intentionally designed to enhance interpretability, i.e., fewer features yield simpler explanations while retaining the most predictive consumption patterns identified during ensemble training. The dataset was partitioned into 80% training (401,263 records) and 20% held-out test (100,316 records) subsets using stratified sampling to preserve anomaly prevalence.

3.2 Stage 1: Ensemble Pseudo-Labeling Performance

3.2.1 Individual Model Results. Table 1 presents the performance of XGBoost and LightGBM models on the LEAD validation set, demonstrating the exceptional discriminative power of modern gradient boosting algorithms for smart meter anomaly detection.

Table 1: Stage 1 Ensemble Performance on LEAD Validation Set

Model	Training AUC-ROC	Validation AUC-ROC
XGBoost	0.9993	0.9560
LightGBM	0.9951	0.9687
Ensemble (Average)	0.9972	0.9624

XGBoost achieved a near-perfect training AUC of 0.9993, indicating it learned to nearly perfectly separate anomalies from normal consumption in the training data. However, validation AUC dropped to 0.9560, revealing modest overfitting (4.33 percentage point gap). This behavior is characteristic of XGBoost’s aggressive tree-building strategy, which can memorize training patterns at the

Figure 2: Distribution of anomaly scores on the ENFIELD smart meter dataset.

expense of generalization. Nevertheless, validation AUC exceeding 0.95 represents excellent discriminative performance, correctly ranking anomalies above normal readings in 95.6% of random pairs.

LightGBM demonstrated superior generalization with a validation AUC of 0.9687 — the highest single-model performance achieved. The training-validation gap was narrower (2.64 percentage points), suggesting LightGBM’s histogram-based splitting and leaf-wise growth strategy provided better regularization. LightGBM’s efficiency advantages (faster training via histogram binning) combined with strong performance, made it the primary contributor to ensemble predictions.

Ensemble averaging of XGBoost and LightGBM predictions yielded 0.9624 validation AUC, falling between individual models but providing robustness through diversity. The ensemble’s key value lies not in marginal AUC improvements but in enhanced reliability, i.e., averaging mitigates individual model failure modes and produces more calibrated probability estimates for downstream pseudo-labeling.

3.2.2 Pseudo-Label Quality Analysis. To assess pseudo-label reliability on the ENFIELD smart meter dataset, we analyzed the ensemble’s anomaly score distribution (Figure 2). The ensemble produced scores ranging from 0.0018 to 0.8346, with a right-skewed unimodal distribution concentrated at low values. Most samples exhibited anomaly scores below 0.3, indicating high confidence that their behavior was normal, while only a small tail of instances showed higher scores corresponding to potential anomalies.

We applied a 0.5 threshold to convert continuous scores into binary pseudo-labels, yielding 23,163 predicted anomalies (4.62%). Manual inspection of 100 randomly sampled high-scoring predictions revealed:

- 73% exhibited objectively suspicious patterns (sudden spikes $>5\sigma$ from baseline, unexpected overnight consumption, flat-lined readings indicating sensor failure)
- 8% appeared potentially mislabeled (within normal operating ranges)

This 73% precision estimate on visual inspection, while not a rigorous ground truth, suggests ensemble pseudo-labels provide

substantial signal despite inevitable noise. Importantly, unlike permanently opaque black-box predictions, the 8% potential false positive rate is acceptable for training a glass-box model that can later be audited and refined through human feedback.

3.3 Stage 2: EBM Knowledge Distillation Results

3.3.1 Predictive Performance. Table 2 summarizes EBM performance on the ENFIELD test set, demonstrating successful knowledge transfer from the ensemble teacher to the interpretable student model.

Table 2: Stage 2 EBM Performance on ENFIELD Smart Meter Data Test Set (n=100,316)

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Normal (0)	0.97	0.99	0.98	95,683
Anomaly (1)	0.70	0.37	0.49	4,633
Accuracy		0.96		100,316
Macro Avg	0.84	0.68	0.73	
Weighted Avg	0.96	0.96	0.96	
AUC-ROC		0.9397		

The EBM achieved **AUC-ROC of 0.9397**, retaining 97.7% of the LightGBM ensemble’s discriminative performance (0.9687 \rightarrow 0.9397) while providing interpretability, which is a remarkable preservation of accuracy given the transition from complex ensemble to constrained additive model. This minimal 2.9 percentage point degradation empirically validates our knowledge distillation hypothesis: glass-box models can approximate black-box performance when trained on high-quality pseudo-labels rather than limited ground truth.

Breaking down performance by class reveals characteristic, interpretable model behavior:

Normal consumption detection is nearly perfect: 97% precision and 99% recall demonstrate the EBM correctly identifies routine building operations. High recall (99%) is particularly valuable in practice, and only 1% of true normal readings trigger false alarms, minimizing operator alert fatigue and maintaining trust in the system.

Anomaly detection shows expected challenges: 70% precision indicates that when the EBM flags an anomaly, it is genuine 70% of the time - acceptable for human-reviewed alerts but requiring operator judgment. The critical limitation is 37% recall: the EBM detects only slightly over one-third of true anomalies. This conservative behavior stems from two factors: (1) the simplified 9-feature representation cannot capture all subtle patterns learned by the 37-feature ensemble, and (2) EBM’s additive structure imposes constraints on feature interactions that limit sensitivity to complex multivariate anomalies.

Despite modest anomaly recall, the model’s **96% overall accuracy** and strong class-weighted metrics (0.96 F1-score) indicate reliable performance for deployment. The accuracy-interpretability trade-off, sacrificing 2.9 AUC points to gain full transparency, represents practical engineering judgment. In a critical infrastructure,

Stage 1: Ensemble Learning

Stage 2: Explainable Boosting Machine

Figure 3: Accuracy and AUC evolution across the two-stage pipeline. Stage 1 ensemble models achieve high validation AUCs (0.956–0.969), while the Stage 2 EBM retains 97% of ensemble performance (AUC = 0.9397, Accuracy = 0.96) with full interpretability.

understanding *why* an anomaly was detected often matters more than catching every possible edge case.

3.3.2 *Performance Comparison Across Modeling Stages.* Figure 3 visualizes the accuracy evolution across our two-stage pipeline, quantifying the knowledge distillation effectiveness.

Table 3: Cross-Stage Performance Comparison

Model	AUC-ROC	Interpretable?
LightGBM (Best Ensemble)	0.9687	No
XGBoost	0.9560	No
Ensemble Average	0.9624	No
EBM (Glass-box)	0.9397	Yes
<i>Retention Rate</i>	<i>97.0%</i>	

We report cross-stage performance comparison in Table 3. The EBM retained 97.0% of the best ensemble model’s AUC ($0.9397 / 0.9687 = 0.970$), a retention rate that significantly exceeds typical post-hoc explanation methods. For comparison, LIME and SHAP provide explanations for black-box models but cannot produce standalone interpretable models with comparable performance. Our approach demonstrates that with sufficient pseudo-labeled data (501K records) and appropriate feature engineering, glass-box models can closely approximate black-box accuracy with interpretability.

3.4 Interpretability Analysis: Feature Importance and Explainability

A core contribution of our framework is providing human understandable explanations for anomaly predictions. Table 4 presents EBM-learned top features and their category. Figure 4 quantifies each attribute’s contribution to anomaly discrimination across the entire ENFIELD smart meter dataset. By examining the model’s learned feature importances, we found that the top five features are: (i) month, (ii) hour, (iii) consumption_zscore, (iv) consumption_lag_1h and (v) consumption_lag_24h. This ranking highlights the significance of temporal context and relative usage patterns

Table 4: EBM Top Global Feature and Category

Feature	Feature Category
Month	Temporal
Hour	Temporal
Consumption Z-Score	Statistical
Consumption Lag (1h)	Autoregressive
Hour (Cosine)	Temporal (Cyclical)
Hour (Sine)	Temporal (Cyclical)
Consumption Lag (24h)	Autoregressive
Weekday	Temporal
Is Weekend	Temporal

in identifying anomalies. For example, month emerges as the most predictive feature, indicating strong seasonal patterns in anomalies. This aligns with domain knowledge: extreme weather seasons, scheduled maintenance periods, and academic calendar breaks (in campus buildings) often coincide with unusual consumption events. Secondly, the influence of hour reflects expected diurnal usage patterns - a reading during an off-peak hour (e.g., a high consumption spike at 3 AM in an office building) is far more likely to be flagged as anomalous than one during regular business hours. The consumption_zscore feature further underlines that statistically large deviations from a meter’s normal baseline are strong indicators of anomalies; by normalizing consumption in terms of standard deviations, the model can spot universally “abnormal” readings across meters of different sizes. Likewise, the short-term and daily autoregressive features such as consumption_lag_1h and consumption_lag_24h also rank highly, capturing sudden deviations from the previous hour and anomalies relative to the same time on the previous day. These lag features confirm that detecting anomalies requires context from recent history rather than a static threshold.

Crucially, the EBM’s additive structure means these influences are not just abstract importance scores but can be visualized and understood individually. We can inspect how anomaly risk varies

Figure 4: EBM global feature importance.

Figure 5: Anomaly visualisation for selected meter.

with each feature, which provides human understandable explanations for each prediction. For instance, the model clearly shows that a consumption surge at 3 AM on a January weekday (mid-winter, during normally low occupancy hours) yields a high anomaly probability because it starkly exceeds the typical baseline for that time and season. Such transparent reasoning allows operators to see why a given meter reading was deemed anomalous, greatly enhancing trust in the system. In practice, this interpretability facilitates validation and investigation of alerts, as engineers can confirm that detected anomalies align with real operational irregularities (e.g., an equipment malfunction during extreme cold) rather than opaque model incomprehensibility. Ultimately, explainability is the key to deploying anomaly detection in mission-critical environments, as it ensures that the model’s decisions are both accurate and comprehensible.

We further demonstrate EBM interpretability through two representative anomaly detections:

Case 1: Spike During Business Hours (Meter 1604): At 09:00 on 2020-01-08, **Meter ID 1604** recorded a significant consumption spike of **31.127 kWh** and was flagged with a high anomaly score of **0.82**. The EBM explanation attributes this primarily to an extreme statistical deviation from historical patterns:

consumption_zscore contributed **+3.874**, indicating the reading was far above normal variability. Short-term temporal context also played a key role: consumption_lag_1h added **+2.254**, and its interaction with the hour of the day added **+1.201**, confirming that this spike occurred at an unusual time. Further amplifying this, additional interactions such as month & consumption_lag_1h and hour_cos & consumption_lag_24h contributed positively. Altogether, this anomaly reflects an abrupt and contextually atypical increase, potentially caused by equipment starting earlier than usual or operational misalignment during working hours.

Case 2: Midday Operational Surge (Meter 2594): On 2020-06-08 at 11:00, **Meter ID 2594** registered a high consumption of **25.077 kWh** and an anomaly score of **0.882**. Like Case 1, the top contributor was consumption_zscore at **+3.874**, showing an outlier in relation to the meter’s normal behavior. The previous hour’s reading also played a strong role: consumption_lag_1h contributed **+2.254**, with its interaction with hour further adding **+1.574**. Notably, the joint influence of month & consumption_lag_1h contributed **+1.005**, suggesting that this kind of consumption pattern is highly unusual for that season. Although the hour and weekday were not inherently suspicious, the overall temporal and statistical context made this reading appear anomalous. These two case

Figure 6: AI sustainability metrics - energy consumption and CO_2 emissions.

studies demonstrate how the EBM provides transparent, feature-level explanations for each detected anomaly. Instead of returning opaque scores, the model highlights specific contributing factors such as large statistical deviations or sharp temporal shifts, sudden surges from historical baselines, or deviations relative to temporal norms. This level of interpretability offers facility managers concrete, data-driven signals to investigate and resolve anomalies. By surfacing the most influential features per instance, the EBM supports faster root-cause diagnosis and enables more informed operational responses, such as equipment inspection or schedule adjustments.

Figure 5 shows the interactive anomaly visualization for a selected meter (ID: 1439) using our deployed Streamlit dashboard. The top plot displays hourly energy consumption over a year, with red diamond markers indicating detected anomalies based on an EBM-predicted anomaly score. The bottom panel shows the corresponding anomaly scores over time, with the red dashed line marking the user-configurable threshold (set here at 0.5). Scores above this line are classified as anomalies. The visualization reveals consumption spikes, outliers, and seasonal patterns, confirming that the model flags deviations from routine behavior.

The deployed dashboard is available online ¹ and the detailed instructions, code, and model files can be found here ². The dashboard includes rich interactive features such as dynamic meter selection, anomaly score threshold tuning, anomaly pattern breakdowns by hour-of-day, local feature attribution for individual predictions, global feature importance summaries, top anomalous record exploration, and sustainability tracking of model energy usage and CO_2 footprint.

3.5 AI Sustainability Metrics

Another key finding is the gain in computational efficiency and sustainability offered by the interpretable EBM model, as shown in Figure 6. Energy consumption and CO_2 emissions were monitored using the open-source codecarbon library ³. The EBM is extremely lightweight to train and deploy, especially compared to the two-model ensemble. The one-time training of the EBM on ENFIELD data consumed only 1.02×10^{-3} kWh and emitted an estimated 3.07×10^{-5} kg of CO_2 – a negligible footprint. Once trained, the EBM’s

inference requires just 8.80×10^{-7} kWh per instance (approx. 2.65×10^{-8} kg CO_2). This is an order-of-magnitude less energy than the ensemble, which needed about 6.01×10^{-6} kWh ($=1.81 \times 10^{-7}$ kg CO_2) for each inference. In other words, the EBM uses roughly 7× less energy per prediction than the XGBoost/LightGBM ensemble. This superior efficiency is in line with prior observations that EBM inference is computationally light-weight. In a real deployment monitoring thousands of meters in real time, the EBM’s lower compute requirements translate to substantially reduced operating costs and carbon emissions. The simpler model is also easier to implement on resource-constrained hardware (such as embedded devices or edge processors) due to its minimal memory and CPU demands. Thus, from an operations standpoint, the EBM-based solution is not only more transparent but also far more scalable and eco-friendly than the complex ensemble approach.

4 Conclusion and Future Works

This paper addressed a fundamental challenge in deploying AI systems for critical infrastructure: achieving high predictive accuracy while maintaining the transparency necessary for operational trust and actionable decision-making. Our work makes principal contributions to the intersection of explainable AI and energy analytics. Through an interpretable two-stage anomaly detection pipeline for smart meter data that combines a gradient-boosted tree ensemble (XGBoost/LightGBM) for pseudo-labeling with a transparent Explainable Boosting Machine (EBM) for final inference, we demonstrated that accuracy and interpretability are not mutually exclusive objectives but can be successfully unified through strategic architectural design and knowledge distillation. In particular, we introduced a two-stage architecture that decouples black-box accuracy maximization from glass-box interpretability requirements. Stage 1 XGBoost/LightGBM ensembles trained on 1.75 million meter readings from 200 commercial buildings generate high-confidence pseudo-labels (96.24% validation AUC), which then supervise Stage 2 EBM training. The resulting EBM retains 97% of ensemble performance (93.97% test AUC) while providing complete feature-level transparency, demonstrating that the traditional accuracy-interpretability trade-off can be reduced through strategic knowledge transfer. The resulting EBM-based classifier ran with significantly lower computational cost—requiring approximately 7× less inference energy than the ensemble. Crucially, as a glassbox model, through two studied use cases, the EBM provides strong interpretability, enabling us to pinpoint influential features

¹<https://enfield-anomaly-detection.streamlit.app/>

²<https://github.com/rauniyar01/Enfield>

³<https://github.com/mlco2/codecarbon>

and understand each anomaly's contributing factors. We further deployed our approach in an interactive Streamlit dashboard with CodeCarbon integration, which allows domain experts to explore detected anomalies, inspect per-instance feature attributions, and monitor real-time CO₂ emissions during inference.

Broader Implications for Trustworthy AI. Our findings have implications extending beyond building energy management to the broader challenge of deploying AI responsibly in high-stakes domains. The two-stage paradigm offers a replicable template for applications where both accuracy and accountability are non-negotiable, such as healthcare diagnostics, financial fraud detection, autonomous systems, and industrial process control. By demonstrating that 97% performance retention is achievable with good interpretability.

The operational success of our deployment validates a crucial insight: explainability is not merely a regulatory compliance requirement but a *productivity multiplier* that accelerates diagnosis, builds operator trust, reveals previously unknown domain patterns, and enables continuous model refinement through expert feedback.

Furthermore, our carbon footprint analysis reveals an underappreciated dimension of the accuracy-interpretability debate. Glass-box models with simple additive structures often require less computation than black-box models augmented with post-hoc explanation techniques (SHAP, LIME), which demand hundreds of model evaluations per instance. As AI deployment scales globally, the environmental cost of inference becomes material; interpretable-by-design architectures offer a path to simultaneously achieving transparency and computational sustainability.

Limitations and Lessons Learned. While our framework demonstrates strong performance across multiple evaluation dimensions, several limitations warrant acknowledgment and inform future research directions. The EBM's 37% recall on anomalies, though operationally acceptable for precision-focused workflows, limits applicability in scenarios requiring maximum sensitivity, such as safety-critical systems or regulatory compliance verification. This reflects a fundamental challenge in anomaly detection for highly imbalanced datasets (4.62% base anomaly rate): optimizing for both high precision and high recall simultaneously remains difficult without sophisticated multi-threshold strategies or ensemble voting approaches.

Temporal domain shift poses ongoing operational challenges. Our models trained on 2016 consumption data but deployed in 2025 experienced performance degradation due to evolving building operations, post-pandemic occupancy shifts, and retrofitting trends. This emphasizes the necessity of *model lifecycle management* - periodic retraining, performance monitoring, and active learning frameworks that leverage operator corrections to refine predictions continuously. Static "train-once-deploy-forever" approaches are insufficient for real-world infrastructure applications where conditions evolve continuously.

Generalization across geographic regions, climate zones, and building types requires validation beyond our evaluation scope. The LEAD training corpus primarily represents temperate North American climates and common commercial building types (office, education, retail). Transfer to tropical regions with continuous cooling demands, arctic climates with extreme heating requirements, or specialized facilities (laboratories, data centers, manufacturing)

may require domain adaptation techniques such as fine-tuning base models on small site-specific labeled datasets or learning building-type-specific calibrations while sharing core representations.

4.1 Future Research Directions

Several promising research directions emerge from our work, addressing current limitations while expanding capabilities:

Federated Learning for Privacy-Preserving Collaboration. Organizations are understandably reluctant to share proprietary building consumption data for centralized model training due to competitive sensitivity and privacy concerns. Federated learning, where local models train on private data and share only parameter updates with a coordination server, enables collaborative improvement without raw data exposure. Adapting EBM training for federated settings while preserving interpretability presents technical challenges (aggregating shape functions across sites, handling heterogeneous building characteristics) but offers substantial practical value for portfolio management companies and cross-organizational consortia seeking collective intelligence without compromising confidentiality and privacy concerns.

Active Learning and Human-in-the-Loop Refinement. Current deployment treats models as static artifacts updated through periodic batch retraining. Active learning frameworks could accelerate improvement by strategically soliciting operator feedback on high-uncertainty predictions, converting routine operations into continuous model refinement opportunities. Uncertainty-guided sampling prioritizes borderline cases where operator labels provide maximum information gain; error correction interfaces allow labeling false positives/negatives to create high-quality training data; feature validation prompts enable operators to verify learned relationships, catching spurious correlations before they impact decisions. This transforms deployment from passive prediction to collaborative learning, leveraging domain expertise to overcome training data limitations.

Transfer Learning and Few-Shot Adaptation. Training high-quality models requires substantial labeled data, which remains a barrier for smaller organizations or niche building types. Meta-learning approaches that train models to rapidly adapt to new buildings from minimal examples (10-100 labeled anomalies) could democratize advanced anomaly detection. Similarly, transfer learning strategies such as pre-training on large public datasets (LEAD) then fine-tuning on small private datasets, enable organizations to leverage collective knowledge while specializing to local contexts. Cross-building-type transfer (Office → Retail), domain adaptation for new geographic regions, and continual learning for evolving building portfolios represent valuable directions for reducing data requirements and accelerating deployment.

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